

MULTI AXIAL TESTING OF ADHESIVELY BONDED JOINTS OF FIBER REINFORCED THERMOPLASTIC POLYMERS

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ABSTRACT

In order to predict the mechanical behavior of adhesively bonded joints, it is necessary to develop robust numerical models. This robustness is only reached if an extensive experimental database with tensile, shear and complex combined peel and shear loads can be established.

The purpose of this study is to present a multi axial device for testing adhesively bonded joints, using KS2-type specimens traditionally utilized for spot-weld characterization. The tests were conducted on a glass fiber reinforced thermoplastic polymer (PA6-6) composite adhesively bonded with a flexible polyurethane adhesive. This adhesive/substrate combination allows short process times and good performances. This experimental study investigates the effects of axial and shear load, loading speed, temperature and adhesive thickness on the mechanical properties of the joints which are compared in terms of stiffness and ultimate strength.

Results show that the strength of the assemblies largely depends on the load orientation, the joint thickness, the loading speed and also the test temperature.

1 INTRODUCTION

In the transportation sector, lightweighting is one way toward the reduction of CO₂ emissions. The low density and good mechanical properties of glass fiber reinforced thermoplastic polymers, coupled to a short manufacturing cycle time make them good candidates for such a weight reduction [1]. When joining these composite parts, adhesive bonding is often preferred to existing standard methods like welding or mechanical joining with rivets or bolts. Bonding allows also multi material joining and avoids local weakening of the structures.

Car makers introduced adhesive since decades to improve crash and NVH (Noise, Vibration, and Harshness) features of their steel structures [2]. Until today, rigid adhesives (epoxy) have often been used. However flexible adhesives (polyurethane, methacrylate) are increasingly used in automotive industry to bond parts like windshield, rear trunks or roofs.

Loureiro *et al* [3] showed that, for large parts assembly, flexible adhesive joints of high thickness (1-5 mm) can meet crash requirements. Moreover, these adhesives present the added benefits of minimizing thermal stresses and filling gaps of varying sizes between parts.

Among the different specimen geometries used for testing adhesively bonded joints, single lap joint test or Thick Adherent Shear Test (TAST) are very common. These types of tests traditionally focus on shear behavior of joints for small adhesive thickness (< 2 mm). In order to provide experimental results for establishing FEA models of the joints, it is necessary to investigate different combinations of tensile and shear loads.

Often based on Arcan [4] fixture system, many multi-axial devices have been developed. They have been used for isotropic and non-isotropic material characterization [5], but also for adhesive fracture toughness characterization [6-8] and more recently for adhesive characterization with improved sample geometry by Cognard *et al.* [9, 10]. The KS2 specimen geometry (U-shaped substrates) developed by Rohde *et al.* [11] for spotweld characterization is on the other hand appropriate when using moderately thin substrates like composite plates. The joint configuration allows for various adhesive/substrate combinations along with a good control of adhesive thickness.

This study presents such a multi-axial testing device and its associated equipment. The main goal is to characterize behaviors of adhesively bonded joints of glass fiber reinforced thermoplastic polymer, under varying experimental conditions. The loading direction investigated are pure shear, pure tensile and shear/tensile loads. Experimental results are presented and discussed.

2 MATERIALS AND TEST SET UP

2.1 Materials

The substrates are made from EVOLITE™ (Solvay) which is a thermoplastic resin (polyamide 6-6) reinforced with woven glass fibers (8H Satin). The plates from which the samples are stamped are 2 mm thick. The elastic behavior is orthotropic, with a tensile modulus of 25 GPa in each principal direction and an ultimate strength of 500 MPa.

The flexible adhesive used in this study is a one component polyurethane Sikaflex®-271 (Sika), which cures when exposed to ambient moisture or by reaction with Sika® Booster 20W. It exhibits a hyper elastic behavior with a Young modulus of 6 MPa and a nominal shear strength of approximately 5 MPa. The nominal glass transition temperature is -50°C (ISO 4663). This adhesive is designed to be used in moderately thick layers.

2.2 Specimens and assemblies manufacturing

Consolidated plates made from 5 plies of thermoplastic composite were thermo-stamped to form U-shaped beams, along the 0° direction of the laminate. Then the samples were cut with a diamond saw (Fig. 1a). The length of the substrates is 70 mm, and their width is 36 mm. Holes were drilled in the flanges in order to bolt the samples to the grips. A specific bonding fixture system was designed to ensure a precise control of the substrate relative positions. A well delimited bonding surface (60 mm x 20 mm) and thickness (0.5 mm or 2 mm in this study) are achieved by using PTFE coated spacers. The final assembly is presented Fig. 1b.

Figure 1: U-shaped substrates: a) stamped U-beam; b) bonded joint.

2.3 Test procedure

The adhesively bonded joints were tested using a multi axial fixture system. This device allows various loading directions, from pure tensile ($\varphi = 90^\circ$), to mixed compression-shear ($\varphi = -45^\circ$). These angles are measured between the plane of the adhesive layer and the loading direction, as in the case of spotweld characterization (Fig. 2).

Figure 2: Multi axial fixture system and loading directions.

This device is mounted in a tensile testing machine (MTS Insight 300) equipped with a 10 kN load cell and a thermal chamber (Fig. 3).

Displacements are primarily monitored via the crosshead information, but a 3D Data Image Correlation (DiC) system is also used to obtain a complete displacement field, which is useful both for controlling the correct kinematic behavior of the whole system and for later numerical modelling. The DiC software is able to compute the strain field in the adhesive up to 100%. For higher strains, the speckle pattern becomes too deformed (Fig. 4).

Figure 3: Assembly mounted in the tensile test machine with DiC system.

Figure 4: Deformation observed during tensile loading: a) initial; b) before failure.

The baseline tests were performed at a loading speed of 3 mm/min, at room temperature (23 °C), with a 2 mm thick adhesive layer, in three loading directions from pure shear to pure tensile load ($\varphi = 0^\circ$, $\varphi = 45^\circ$ and $\varphi = 90^\circ$). The influence of various parameters was then investigated. This is summed up in Table 1.

Loading Direction (φ)	Loading Speed	Temperature	Adhesive Thickness
0°	3 mm/min	23 °C	0.5 mm
45°	50 mm/min	80 °C	2 mm
90°	500 mm/min		

Table 1: Experimental parameters.

3 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

For each configuration, a minimum of three samples were tested. On the whole, the scattering was very low and always less than 10 %. Experimental results are analyzed in terms of force/displacement curves and ultimate strengths. Fracture patterns are also examined.

3.1 Baseline results: influence of loading direction

Three loads orientations are tested with the reference configuration: tensile ($\varphi = 90^\circ$), shear ($\varphi = 0^\circ$) and a combined tensile/shear ($\varphi = 45^\circ$) load. Tensile curves are the stiffest ones. They exhibit a bi-linear behavior with an inflection point around 2/3 of ultimate strength (Fig. 5). The average tensile stress at failure is around 5 MPa, which is slightly lower than the failure stress of the adhesive alone. Hyper elastic behavior is observed under shear mode. The average shear stress at failure is around 4 MPa. A hyper elastic behavior can also be observed for combined shear/tensile mode. Ultimate strengths are similar to tensile mode. The lowest ultimate strength is obtained with the shear mode.

Figure 5: Typical force/displacement curves, adhesive thickness = 2 mm, temperature 23 °C.

Displacements at failure are of the same order of magnitude for all loading directions. The stored energy (the area under Force-Displacement curve before failure) is lower (~15%) for shear loads.

The fracture patterns for each configuration are presented (Fig. 6). A first comment to be made is that the fracture is cohesive in every performed test, which indicates a good adhesion between the substrate and the adhesive. Each loading direction leads to its own characteristic fracture pattern. Tensile loading fracture surface (Fig. 6a) shows circular marks which are typical of cavities nucleation. This cavitation phenomenon could be linked to the change of slope observed in the force displacement curve, indicating damage initiation. Pure shear loading leads to a failed surface presenting very fine and regular parallel marks (Fig. 6c). The fracture pattern is more complex for the combined tensile/shear loading (Fig. 6b). The aspect is rougher and less regular and does not present the characteristic features found in both previous cases.

Figure 6: Typical fracture patterns: a) tensile loads $\varphi = 90^\circ$; b) combined load $\varphi = 45^\circ$; c) shear load $\varphi = 0^\circ$.

3.2 Influence of loading speed

The loading speed was increased to $V=50$ mm/min and $V=500$ mm/min. The scattering of the results is low. Representative curves for each speed and for each orientation are presented Fig. 7.

Figure 7: Effect of loading speed: a) tensile loads $\varphi = 90^\circ$; b) combined load $\varphi = 45^\circ$; c) shear load $\varphi = 0^\circ$.

Increasing the loading speed always leads to increased stiffness and ultimate strength. This effect is more pronounced when shear loading is present. In the pure shear loading case, the apparent stiffness is increased by 40 % for a loading speed of 500 mm/min. This effect can be linked to a viscous behavior of the adhesive.

To underline this behavior, it is interesting to plot the strength results in the tensile-shear loading plane (Fig. 8).

Figure 8: Effect of loading speed on the failure envelope.

The fracture patterns observed for higher speeds (Fig. 9) are very similar to those obtained with the quasi static loading. Tensile and shear loading lead to very different fractured surface appearances, but the shear-tensile mode loading shows also some of the fine parallel marks associated with pure shear mode.

Figure 9: Fracture patterns for V=50 mm/min and V=500 mm/min.

3.3 Influence of temperature

The same tests were performed at a temperature of 80 °C for the three previous loading speeds. Results are presented Fig. 10-12.

Regardless of the loading speed, increasing the temperature causes a dramatic drop of the force and the maximum displacement at failure which are both reduced by half. This contraction of the failure envelope is presented Fig. 13 in the case of a 3 mm/min loading speed.

At quasi static loading speed, a stiffness reduction is only observed for the tensile loading direction. This softening phenomenon due to elevated temperature becomes more marked for all directions at higher loading speeds.

Figure 10: Effect of temperature (loading speed 3 mm/min): a) 90°; b) 45°; c) 0°.

Figure 11: Effect of temperature (loading speed 50 mm/min): a) 90°; b) 45°; c) 0°.

Figure 12: Effect of temperature (loading speed 500 mm/min): a) 90°; b) 45°; c) 0°.

Figure 13: Effect of temperature on the failure envelope ($V = 3 \text{ mm/min}$)

The fracture patterns are also affected by the test temperature (Fig. 14). At 80 °C, the cavities observed at 23 °C on the fractured surfaces in pure tensile loading are no more present. The surface are rougher, with less fine features. In pure shear mode, the surface is smoother but the parallel marks are less fine and less visible than at room temperature.

Figure 14: Fracture profile at $T=80^\circ\text{C}$.

3.4 Joint thickness effect

Joint thickness influence was studied at room temperature and quasi static loading speed. The curves obtained for 2 mm and 0.5 mm thickness are presented (Fig. 15). Thinner glue layer is associated with an increase in both the strength and the stiffness of the assemblies for each orientation. This effect is more pronounced for shear loading (20 %). On the other hand, as expected for a lower adhesive volume, the ultimate displacements are strongly reduced.

Figure 15: Effect of joint thickness reduction.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the behaviour of an adhesively bonded joint composed of a flexible polyurethane adhesive and glass reinforced thermoplastic substrates was characterized. To this purpose, a specific fixture system has been developed. It allows various loading directions and is designed to accommodate KS2 type specimens. An associated bonding jig allows an accurate relative positioning of the substrates and a precise control of the shape and thickness of the adhesive layer.

Experimental results obtained with this system show the influence of various parameters on the strength and stiffness of the assemblies. At room temperature and quasi static loading, the shape of the load-displacement curves depends on the load orientation. Pure shear loading leads to the lowest ultimate strength. Furthermore, specific patterns in fractured surfaces are associated to these different loading directions.

Increasing the loading speed significantly increases the strength and stiffness of the assemblies without reducing much the ultimate displacement. On the other hand, tests conducted at elevated temperature (80 °C) show a strong reduction of both strength and displacement.

Reducing the joint thickness below the recommended dimension is not detrimental to the assembly strength or stiffness, which are both increased, but the joint flexibility is strongly reduced.

These experimental results allow to establish various parameterized failure envelopes in the tensile-shear plane. This database is needed to define a robust model suitable for large scale simulations.

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